

UREAURETHANES WITH ADDITION OF BOEHMITE

K. Pietrzak^{1*}, J. Ryszkowska¹¹ Faculty of Materials Science and Engineering, Warsaw University of Technology, Woloska 141, 02-507 Warsaw, Poland* Corresponding author (kpietrzak@inmat.pw.edu.pl)**Keywords:** ureaurethanes, one-step method, dicyandiamide, boehmite, transport in mines**1 Introduction**

For many years now polyurethanes (PUR) have been used in many branches of industry such as transport, mining, engineering and medicine. The reasons of the great demand for these materials are their functional properties, i.e. good resistance to abrasion and to oil, grease and weather conditions. The properties are the result of their segmented structure [1]. Ureaurethanes (PUUR) belong to this group of polymers [2]. Their macroparticles contain, beside urethane group, also urea groups. These materials were intended to be used in mining machines tyres. Machines used in mines including the ones of suspended nature are exposed to very high loads. They operate in considerable dustiness and changeable temperatures between -40°C and +50°C. And it is tyres that wear the quickest.

To ensure a continuous operation of mining transport machines as well as safety of mining teams it is necessary to work out a new material guaranteeing the manufacture of wheels characterised by higher operation parameters. For this reason it was suggested that such tyres be produced, using a continuous method, from ureaurethane elastomers for the manufacture of which dicyandiamide (DIDY) [3] is used. The application of DIDY causes the appearance of substituent in the form of highly polar imidonitrile group in every constitutional unit of hard segment of these PUURs' macroparticles. Owing to this structure they are characterised by such advantageous properties like high tear strength and tensile modulus. Such polyurethanes are also distinguished by high resistance to hydrolysis, low water absorption and high resistance to abrasive wear. In the case of materials intended for the use in mining the thermal resistance is essential. Both thermal and fire resistance are important, especially in mining. In order to improve PUURs' stability and thermal

resistance we can change the substrate for their production, their proportions, mix them with polymers of higher thermal resistance, modify their surface and add the fillers; these methods can also be applied jointly.

One of the modification methods of polyurethane elastomers, including PUUR, is the use of nanofillers thus improving thermal and mechanical properties [4,5]. Plate compounds [6,7] are among the nanofillers used as flame retardants or flammability reducers. Recently, boehmite – oxoaluminium hydroxide is reported to be used for PUR modification (γ - AlOOH) [8-10]. The compound is the main ingredient of bauxite. In nature it can occur in two crystal forms namely as diaspore - α -AlOOH and boehmite γ -AlOOH [11]. AlOOH can be obtained through annealing crystalline forms of aluminium hydroxide Al(OH)₃. Aluminium compounds occurring in nature contain numerous impurities of large sizes and variability of shapes. Therefore, many firms offer synthetic Al compounds with controlled shape and particle size [12].

During combustion of polymer composites with Al(OH)₃ water is liberated. This causes combustion delay and lowering of the initial temperature of thermal degradation of polymers. The liberated vapour gets into the combustion zone in the flame where the concentration of flammable gases and oxygen decreases. The occurring metallic oxides form a layer on the composite's surface and limit the spread of volatile products of decomposition to the flame thus slowing the burning of the materials. The mechanism of flammability limitation in the case of boehmite, form of Al(OH)₃ is similar, as confirmed by previous investigations [4]. This compound is cheap and easily available and applying its nanoparticles can result in obtaining favourable properties while using just small quantities of it. As

part of the study boehmite and boehmite modified with aluminium diethylphosphate were used for PUUR modification.

2 Experimental

2.1 Samples

For the manufacture of PUUR the following components were used: poly(ethylene adipate) (PAE) with molar mass average ca 1950 g/mol - Alfaster T620 (Alfa System), 4,4'-diphenylmethane diisocyanate (MDI) - Aldrich, dicyandiamide (DIDY) – OMNICURE 5 from Emeraldas well as boehmite (AlOOH) – Apyral from Nabaltec and boehmite modified with aluminium diethylphosphate – (KRZ142), produced at the Faculty of Chemistry, Warsaw University of Technology. PUUR synthesis was performed with the following molar ratio: 2 PAE moles, 5 MDI moles and 3 DIDY moles. This molar ratio should lead to formation of macroparticles containing 28% wt of stiff segments. The fillers' share was 5 % vol. The samples were marked as A1-PUUR, A2-PUUR+APYRAL, A3-PUUR+KRZ142.

2.2 Measurements and characterisation

The analyses started with the observation of nanofillers' structure. Next, chemical constitution of produced PUUR and nanocomposites was described along with their thermal analysis, mechanical properties and abrasion.

2.2.1 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

SEM observation was performed on a Hitachi TM3000 microscope. SEM was used to observe the structure of the fillers used in this study. The samples were coated with gold to increase their conductivity. A series of images at different magnifications was acquired.

2.2.2 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)

FT-IR was performed on a Nicolet FT-IR 6700 (using 64 counts) to investigate the chemical structure of PUUR. The analyses were performed using Omnic software, and a baseline correction using CO₂ and H₂O was performed to eliminate the

impact of residues of these compounds from the analysis.

2.2.3 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

DSC was carried out using TA Instrument DSC Q1000. Samples weighing approximately 10 mg were subjected to heat/cool/heat in the temperature range -90°C–260°C, in order to determine the characteristic temperatures.

2.2.4 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

TGA was performed on a TA Instruments TGA Q500 device to verify the thermal stability of the elastomers examined in this study. The analysis was conducted on a sample weighing approximately 10 mg in a N₂ atmosphere, with a heating rate of 10°C/min from room temperature to 600°C.

2.2.5 Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA)

DMA was carried out using TA Instrument DMA Q800. The study was conducted on samples of rectangular, two-point bending method in the temperature range of -100°C–100°C.

2.2.6 Physical and mechanical measurement

The density (ρ) test was conducted using hydrostatic weighing, in accordance with ISO 2781. The hardness (H) test was conducted using a Shore A durometer, according to ASTM D2240-75. Wear resistance (ΔV) was determined according to ISO 4649. The resilience (η) test was conducted using Schober method according to PN-71/C-04255.

2.2.7 Cone calorimeter (CC)

Flammability tests were made using a cone calorimeter under the heat flux equal to 50 kW/m². The samples were 100 mm x 100 mm x 4 mm in size. The CC test was performed in accordance with ISO 5660.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The structures of the fillers used in this study are presented in Fig.1. The magnification of the images is 1000x. Apyral commercial product is a white powder consisting of particles with regular shape

and size of several micrometers (Fig.1a). Boehmite, modified with KRZ142, is a white deposit consisting of fibres 500 nm diameter and several micrometers length (Fig.1b).

3.2 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)

Chemical constitution and structure of the produced materials were analysed using infrared spectroscopy with Fourier (FT-IR).

Ureaurethane elastomers were synthesised in a polyaddition reaction of PAE with MDI. Dicyandiamide (DIDY) was used as a chain extender. Syntheses of ureaurethanes and their composites were correct as indicated by the lack of peak coming from NCO groups with wavenumber 2270 cm^{-1} [13] (Fig.1).

Spectra show bands so characteristic of polyurethanes: coming from stretching vibrations of -N-H groups ranging between $3450\text{--}3330\text{ cm}^{-1}$, coming from symmetrical and asymmetrical stretching vibrations of $-\text{CH}_2$ group with wavenumbers 2934 cm^{-1} and 2850 cm^{-1} [14], I amide band ranging between $1750\text{--}1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ coming from vibrations of carbonyl group C=O [15], II amide band ranging between $1515\text{--}1560\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and III amide band ranging between $1225\text{--}1239\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [16].

DIDY contains two amino groups and one highly polar cyanimine group bonded to the same carbon atom. The polar urea groups ($1680\text{--}1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$) are formed as a result of the reaction of amino and isocyanate groups. The presence of a strong polar urea group and a strong polar nitrylimide side-group in every short hard segment influences the urea-urethane properties.

When analysing the spectra it was found that PUUR and their composites differ in the intensity of vibrations connected with vibrations of III amide band and the band resulting from vibrations of -C-O-C- bond of urethane group.

The PUUR chain is composed of flexible segments and rigid segments. The rigid segments can interact with each other through hydrogen bonds. During this process the rigid segments aggregate and give hard micro – phase. Hard phase is hardly miscible with the soft phase, which has been formed with the use of much less polar soft segments.

The course of this process can be analysed by calculating the degree of phase separation (DPS)

basing on FTIR spectra. Infrared spectroscopy is well established for measuring changes in hydrogen bonding in polyurethanes. The carbonyl hydrogen-bonding index (R) can be determined by analysing the intensities of the carbonyl stretching vibrations of free and hydrogen-bonded groups. Significant changes in carbonyl hydrogen-bonding index allow to observe differences in phase separation and phase mixing [17,18].

For the calculation of DPS, bands intensity values were used from wavenumber range of $1735\text{--}1745\text{ cm}^{-1}$, connected with stretching vibrations of the free group C=O of urethane unit as well as from the range of $1705\text{--}1720\text{ cm}^{-1}$, originating from the vibrations of the corresponding bonded group. Bands $1695\text{--}1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1685\text{--}1694\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were also used, corresponding to the free and bonded C=O group of urea unit. The results of quantitative analysis are shown in Fig. 3. The degree of phase separation for PUUR and nanocomposite with modified boehmite is similar. The introduction of unmodified boehmite into PUUR causes a considerable decrease in DPS.

3.3 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

DSC analysis was conducted for information about glass transition temperature of analysed materials. DSC curves are shown in Fig.4. DSC of analysed materials carried out showed the presence the glass transition temperatures of soft segments (T_{gSS}). Temperature T_{gSS} is similar for all samples and is about -30°C .

3.4 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

Thermal stability of the produced materials was assessed basing on the temperature value of 5% volume loss ($T_{5\%}$) determined on the basis of Fig.5a. This temperature was assumed to be the initial degradation temperature [19].

PUUR, with unmodified boehmite Apyral, shows the highest $T_{5\%}$ of 296°C , which proves of its higher thermal resistance than the other nanocomposite; for PUUR $T_{5\%}$ amounts 293°C , while for PUUR with modified boehmite it reaches 292°C .

In the process of PUUR degradation two degradation stages are observed. The first step of degradation correlates with the maximum rate of degradation of hard segments (T_{max1}) and the second step correlates with the maximum rate of degradation of soft

segments (T_{max2}) (Fig.5b). The introduction of the filler results in changing the thermal characteristic of PUUR. The first step occurs around 310°C and the second step occurs around 360-415°C. It is observed that addition of boehmite into PUUR results in only slight changes in the values of T_{max1} but huge changes in the values of T_{max2} . The temperature of the second stage of nanocomposites' degradation (A2-390°C and A3-416°C) is higher than that of PUUR (A1-365°C).

3.5 Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA)

Dynamic-mechanical thermal analysis was used to evaluate mechanical properties over a wide temperature range. Table 1 lists the values of the elastic modulus set at temperatures -30, 20 and 60°C and the glass transition temperature. The nature of the curves in Fig.6a gives a sudden drop in modulus E' in the narrow range of transition temperatures of the elastomers in highly fragile state. Below the glass transition temperature of soft segments the value of E' depends mainly on the amount of boehmite introduced. After passing the material into a highly flexible state, elastic modulus E' also depends on the mobility of macromolecules [20]. Above 40°C the elasticity modulus increases, which is the result of segment grouping. The highest values of tangent of phase shift angle (Fig.6b) were obtained for samples PUUR with no modifiers. The introduction of nanofiller lowers PUUR elastomer's ability to disperse energy.

3.6 Physical and mechanical measurement

The results of physical and mechanical properties are given in Table 2. The density is very similar for all samples. The hardness is the highest for PUUR with modified boehmite KRZ142, which means that this sample obtained a big amount of hard segments. This PUUR has also the worst resilience.

The composites have high wear resistance. The addition of boehmite caused a significant decrease in wear resistance, which is an unfavourable characteristic for the presented application. This is probably the result of poor dispersion of filler matrix.

3.7 Cone calorimeter (CC)

Improved thermal stability should correspond to the increased stability of polymeric materials under fire conditions [21]. The results of the CC measurements are presented in Fig.7. The initial sections of curves correspond to the period of the tested materials heating, evaporation of volatile products and the creation of flammable gases. We can see a significant difference in the amount of heat released from the polyurethanes modified with boehmite particles compared with pure PUUR. Peaks in the diagrams (Fig.7) indicate combustion of the pyrolysis products with evolution of much heat (maximum heat release rate - HRR_{max}). In PUUR there is one large peak in favour of the separation of large amounts of heat and the other is smaller. For the composite with the addition of boehmite there are two much lower peaks, which indicates a change in the mechanism of combustion. The lowest rate of heat release (HRR_{max}) is found in PUUR with modified boehmite KRZ142, which may be related to the fact that boehmite is known as filler which absorbs heat and leads to the reduction of the HRR_{max} value. Another important parameter delineated using the cone calorimeter is the time to ignition (tig) (Table 1). Time to ignition of composites is longer than that of pure PUUR. This may result from the previous decomposition of organic part present on the surface of the filler not chemically bound to PUUR. The highest value is for PUUR with unmodified boehmite Apyral.

The obtained values were determined HRR_{max} and tig "fireproof protective impact indicator" (HRR_{max}/tig) (FPI), which is used to evaluate the effectiveness of flame retardant compounds. The calculated values are given in Table 2. These data show that the composites have lower FPI. The lowest FPI is observed in the nanocomposites - A3 sample with modified boehmite [21].

4 Conclusions

The introduction of boehmite to ureaurethanes causes changes in chemical structure and consequently in the properties of the materials produced. This is probably because the addition of fillers changes the reaction between the reactive groups of individual substrates. Application to modify the boehmite leads to changes in the course of thermal decomposition and decomposition mechanisms of bonds. The introduction of 5 wt%

boehmite leads to a significant increase in the decomposition temperature of soft segments and a small increase in the decomposition temperature of hard segments. Unfortunately, no improvement have been achieved in mechanical properties and wear resistance, which may be results of matrix connection. Slightly better physico-mechanical properties are observed in the boehmite-modified composite in which the degree of phase separation was higher than in the case of composite with unmodified addition.

The use of modified boehmite makes the resistance of ureaurethanes three times higher than that of PUUR without addition. The use of boehmite as a filler in ureaurethanes for specific applications requires further research to find an optimal composition and manufacturing conditions of the composites.

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Fig.1. SEM images of fillers: a) Apyral, 1000x magnification, b) KRZ142, 1000x magnification

a TM3000_5627 2011-08-26 12:58 N D5,1 x1,0k 100 um

b TM3000_5647 2011-08-26 13:19 N D4,3 x1,0k 100 um

Fig.2. FT-IR spectra of tested ureaurethanes

Fig.3. The degree of phase separation (DPS) of ureaurethanes and nanocomposites

a

Fig.4. DSC curves of tested ureaurethanes

b

Fig.5. a) TG and b) DTG curves of tested ureaurethanes

Fig.6. Curves of a) storage modulus and b) tan delta obtained of DMA analysis

a

b

Table 1. Results of elastic modulus for temperature in which wheels are use and glass transition temperature obtained from DMA curves

Samples	E'_{-30} [MPa]	E'_{20} [MPa]	E'_{60} [MPa]
A1	4320	107	139
A2	2480	25	66
A3	2345	20	211

Table 2. Physical, mechanical and thermal properties of selected PUUR's

Samples	ρ , g/cm ³	H, °ShA	ΔV , mm ³	η , %
A1	1.2525	87	29.9	28
A2	1.2531	89	47.7	28
A3	1.2594	95	45.1	23

Fig.7. Heat release rate curves of ureaurethanes with different additives from CC tests

Table 3. Characteristic parameters of tested PUUR's obtained from CC tests

Samples	HRR_{max}, kW/m ²	tig,s	FPI, kW/sm ²
A1	945.7	22	43
A2	570.5	28	20
A3	349.5	25	14

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